

Computational certification of OEIS A395171(11) and bounds for A395171(18)

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Abstract

OEIS A395171, introduced by Marco Ripà, is defined by taking $A_{395171}(n)$ to be the least integer $m > 1$ such that $\gcd(m^{\text{prime}(n)^k} - 1, m! - 1) > 1$ for every positive integer k . The value A395171(11), corresponding to $\text{prime}(11) = 31$, was previously known through the bound $700000 < A_{395171}(11) \leq 357913941$.

This note gives a computational certification that $A_{395171}(11) = 357913941$. The computation verifies that $\gcd(\Phi_{31}(m), m! - 1) = 1$ for every integer m with $2 \leq m \leq 357913940$, while the final production run finds $\gcd(\Phi_{31}(357913941), 357913941! - 1) = 715827883$. The computation uses an m -first batch method based on product and remainder trees, implemented in C++ with GMP and OpenMP.

The same method was also applied to the case $\text{prime}(18) = 61$, proving the lower bound $A_{395171}(18) > 100000000$. Together with the standard construction from the prime $(2^{61} + 1)/3$, this gives $100000000 < A_{395171}(18) \leq 768614336404564649$. A subsequent q -first search found no witness prime $q \leq 999999963$ for the remaining interval $100000000 < m < 768614336404564649$.

The accompanying archive contains the C++ source code, raw computation logs, a curated interval manifest, and SHA-256 checksums.

1 Definition and reduction

Let p be an odd prime. For this note, define A_p as the least integer $m > 1$, if it exists, such that $\gcd(m^{p^k} - 1, m! - 1) > 1$ for every integer $k \geq 1$. Then OEIS A395171 satisfies

$$A_{395171}(n) = A_{\text{prime}(n)}.$$

For prime p , let

$$\Phi_p(x) = \frac{x^p - 1}{x - 1} = x^{p-1} + x^{p-2} + \cdots + x + 1.$$

The computation uses the following elementary reduction.

Lemma 1. *For $m > 1$ and prime p , the condition*

$$\gcd(m^{p^k} - 1, m! - 1) > 1 \quad \text{for every } k \geq 1$$

is equivalent to

$$\gcd(\Phi_p(m), m! - 1) > 1.$$

Proof. If the condition holds for every $k \geq 1$, it holds in particular for $k = 1$. Conversely, if some integer $d > 1$ divides both $m^p - 1$ and $m! - 1$, then d divides $(m^p)^k - 1 = m^{pk} - 1$ for every $k \geq 1$.

Since $m^p - 1 = (m-1)\Phi_p(m)$, it remains to show that the factor $m-1$ cannot contribute. Every positive divisor of $m-1$ divides $m!$, and therefore cannot divide $m! - 1$. Hence $\gcd(m-1, m! - 1) = 1$, and all common divisors of $m^p - 1$ and $m! - 1$ come from $\Phi_p(m)$. \square

Thus the exact test for a candidate m is whether

$$G_p(m) := \gcd(\Phi_p(m), m! - 1)$$

is greater than 1.

2 The m -first batch algorithm

A direct computation of $m! \bmod \Phi_p(m)$ independently for every m is too slow over large intervals. The computation used here processes a block of consecutive values $L, L + 1, \dots, R$ at once.

For $m \in [L, R]$, set $N_m = \Phi_p(m)$, and let $F = (L - 1)!$. Then $m! = F \cdot L(L + 1) \cdots m$. The algorithm is:

- (1) Compute the moduli $N_m = \Phi_p(m)$ for all $m \in [L, R]$.
- (2) Build a product tree with leaves N_m .
- (3) Use a remainder tree to compute $F \bmod N_m$ simultaneously for all $m \in [L, R]$.
- (4) Scan through the block, maintaining the exact prefix product $P_m = L(L + 1) \cdots m$. For each m , compute

$$m! \bmod N_m = ((F \bmod N_m)(P_m \bmod N_m)) \bmod N_m.$$

- (5) Compute $\gcd(N_m, m! - 1)$. If this gcd is greater than 1, the corresponding m is a solution.

After a block is completed, the exact factorial is updated from $(L - 1)!$ to $R!$ by multiplying by the exact block product $L(L + 1) \cdots R$.

The implementation was written in C++17, using GMP for exact multiple-precision integer arithmetic and OpenMP for parallel parts of the modulus generation and product-tree construction.

Lemma 2. *For every $m \in [L, R]$, the batch algorithm computes the exact value of $m! \bmod \Phi_p(m)$.*

Proof. The product/remainder tree gives $F \bmod N_m$ for every leaf modulus N_m . The prefix product $P_m = L(L + 1) \cdots m$ is maintained exactly. Since $m! = FP_m$, the algorithm computes

$$m! \bmod N_m = ((F \bmod N_m)(P_m \bmod N_m)) \bmod N_m$$

exactly. Therefore the final gcd is precisely $\gcd(\Phi_p(m), m! - 1)$. □

3 Certification of OEIS A395171(11)

For $p = 31$, the computation verified $G_{31}(m) = 1$ for every integer m in the range $2 \leq m \leq 357913940$. The computation was split across several runs and two machines. The raw terminal logs are included in the archive. Since some logs contain truncated lines caused by buffering, manual interruptions, and restarts, the authoritative summary of the certified intervals is the curated file `manifest.csv`.

The intervals in `manifest.csv` were checked manually from complete run headers, complete certification lines, completion summaries, and overlaps between consecutive runs. In particular, the interval $200000000 \leq m < 270000000$ was covered by separate Mac and Windows runs, with overlap, even though it is not contiguous in a single raw log file.

The final production run on the OMEN machine covered the upper part of the range and encountered the first positive value at $m = 357913941$. The relevant output was:

```
[BINGO m-first] Trovato m = 357913941
[TEMPO] 89879.8s dall'inizio batch
[GCD] 715827883
```

Since the code scans each block in increasing order and stops at the first hit, this output also certifies that all preceding values in the same block, up to 357913940, were tested and rejected.

Theorem 1.

$$A395171(11) = 357913941.$$

Proof. By the reduction above, an integer $m > 1$ is admissible for $p = 31$ if and only if $G_{31}(m) > 1$. The m -first computation gives $G_{31}(m) = 1$ for every $2 \leq m \leq 357913940$. The final production run gives $G_{31}(357913941) = 715827883 > 1$. Hence no smaller admissible value exists, and therefore $A395171(11) = 357913941$. \square

4 Additional computation for OEIS A395171(18)

For $p = 61$, corresponding to OEIS A395171(18), the same m -first method completed the interval $2 \leq m \leq 100000000$ without finding a solution. The final output of the run was:

```
[DONE] Intervallo m completato senza trovare soluzioni.
[TOTAL] tempo: 52794.3s
[TOTAL] m certificati in questo run: 99999999
```

Therefore

$$A395171(18) > 100000000.$$

An explicit upper bound follows from a standard construction. If q is a prime divisor of $(2^p + 1)/3$, then $m = q - 2$ is admissible. Indeed, $m \equiv -2 \pmod{q}$, and $2^p \equiv -1 \pmod{q}$, so $m^p \equiv (-2)^p \equiv -2^p \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$. Also, Wilson's theorem gives $(q - 2)! \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$. Hence q divides both $m^p - 1$ and $m! - 1$.

For $p = 61$, the integer

$$q = \frac{2^{61} + 1}{3} = 768614336404564651$$

is prime. Therefore $m = q - 2 = 768614336404564649$ is admissible, giving

$$A395171(18) \leq 768614336404564649.$$

Combining the lower and upper bounds gives

$$100000000 < A395171(18) \leq 768614336404564649.$$

5 The q -first search for OEIS A395171(18)

After the m -first computation proved $A395171(18) > 100000000$, a q -first search was run to look for a smaller upper bound.

The search did not start from small q , because these had already become irrelevant. If q is a prime witness for some remaining solution, then $q \mid m! - 1$. Since no prime $q \leq m$ can divide $m! - 1$, every witness must satisfy $q > m$. After the lower bound $m > 100000000$ was established, every remaining possible witness had to satisfy $q > 100000000$. Also, for $p = 61$, a nontrivial witness prime must satisfy $q \equiv 1 \pmod{61}$; since q is odd, this becomes $q \equiv 1 \pmod{122}$. The first integer above 100000000 satisfying this congruence is 100000107.

The q -first computation searched all candidates $q \equiv 1 \pmod{122}$ from 100000107 through 999999963. For each prime q , it generated the nontrivial roots of $x^{61} \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$, retained only roots m with $100000000 < m < 768614336404564649$, and tested the factorial condition using Wilson's theorem to choose the shorter side between $m!$ and $(q - m - 1)!$.

The final summary of the search was:

```
[DONE] q interval completed.
[TOTAL] time: 16751.1s
[TOTAL] q-candidates: 7377049
[TOTAL] primes q == 1 mod p: 751427
[TOTAL] factorial tests: 33301322
[TOTAL] hits: 0
[BEST] best m found: 768614336404564649
```

Thus the q -first search found no improved upper bound. More precisely, it found no solution m with $100000000 < m < 768614336404564649$ having a prime witness $q \leq 999999963$. This does not rule out solutions in that interval with larger witnesses.

6 Computational data

The main results are summarized in Table 1. Detailed interval coverage is given in the accompanying `manifest.csv`. The raw logs and source files are included in the archive.

Case	Prime p	Method	Result
A395171(11)	31	m -first	no solution for $2 \leq m \leq 357913940$
A395171(11)	31	m -first	hit at $m = 357913941$, $\gcd = 715827883$
A395171(18)	61	m -first	no solution for $2 \leq m \leq 100000000$
A395171(18)	61	q -first	no witness $q \leq 999999963$ found

Table 1: Summary of the computations. The exact run decomposition is given in `manifest.csv`.

The $p = 31$ computation proves

$$A395171(11) = 357913941.$$

The $p = 61$ computations give

$$100000000 < A395171(18) \leq 768614336404564649,$$

and the q -first search found no witness prime $q \leq 999999963$.

7 Reproducibility notes

The archive contains the source files used for the computations. The raw logs are included as generated, including interrupted or partially buffered terminal output. They should therefore not be parsed blindly as one continuous stream. The curated file `manifest.csv` records the certified intervals used for the proof.

The code was compiled with commands of the following form on Linux/WSL:

```
g++ -O3 -march=native -std=c++17 -fopenmp source.cpp \
-lgmpxx -lgmp -o executable
```

The computations used GMP for exact integer arithmetic. SHA-256 checksums for the report, source files, logs, and manifest are included in `checksums.sha256`.

8 Acknowledgements

I thank Marco Ripà for introducing OEIS A395171, for helpful comments, and for suggesting the additional computation for the case $p = 61$.

References

- [1] OEIS Foundation Inc., *The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, A395171. <https://oeis.org/A395171>
- [2] Torbjörn Granlund and the GMP development team, *GNU Multiple Precision Arithmetic Library*. <https://gmplib.org/>